

Adverse soils

Performance of promising salt-tolerant varieties in Karnataka, India

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Rice is the main cereal crop in the lowlands of Vani Vilas Sagar tract, Karnataka. A large proportion of this area is black soils; most are affected by salt. The varieties presently grown are SR26B and S317, known locally as Banku and Halubbalu, respectively. Both have fair tolerance for adverse soils, but they lodge even at preflowering stage. They are also susceptible to blast disease. Some breeding to improve SR26B was

initiated at the Agricultural College, Dhanwar, in 1968. But the improvement was only in earliness and photoperiod insensitivity. The development prompted the testing of new salt-tolerant lines — from crosses involving SR26B, S317, and other rices from various rice research institutes within and outside of the state — for adaptability to the Vani Vilas tract.

During both the 1977 dry and wet seasons 17 MR lines from crosses involving Kare Kagga and SR26B, 3 IRRI varieties, and 1 culture from AICRIP, Hyderabad, were evaluated along with popular local varieties at Alur village. The experiments were in a randomized block design, replicated

three times. Rice was sown on 25 January and 22 July in the 1977 dry and wet seasons, respectively. Three or four 26-day-old seedlings were transplanted at a 20 × 15-cm spacing to accommodate a plot size of 3.6 m².

In the dry season, the cultivars MR353, MR359, MR363, and SR26B-M (a photoperiod-insensitive mutant from SR26B) yielded better than Mangala, the high yielding tolerant check (see table). The three MR rices matured 5 days later than Mangala but 20 days earlier than SR26B-M. In the wet season, the yields of MR353, MR359, and the new entries MR340 and Dasal were comparable with those of SR26B. All varieties matured from 9 to 22 days earlier than SR26B. The mean yields over 2 seasons of MR353, MR359, MR362, and SR26B-M were more than 4 t/ha. The MR cultures clearly owe their tolerance to their female parent Kare Kagga, a popular cultivar on the west coast of Karnataka, India, known for its high tolerance for soil adversities.

Because of their plant stature, earliness, and photoperiod insensitivity, MR340, MR353, MR369, and MR363 have been advanced for multilocational performance testing in Vani Vilas Sagar, Tungabhadra, and Krishnarja Sagar project areas, where soil problems similar to those of Hiriyur prevail in vast areas. ☞

Performance of rice varieties and lines in the salt-affected soils at Alur, Karnataka, India, in the 1977 dry and wet seasons.

Designation	Parentage	Days to maturity	Yield ^a (t/ha)		
			1977 DS	1977 WS	Mean
MR 338	K. Kagga/IR8	120	4.2	1.0	2.6
MR 343	SR 26B/Waner 1	145	4.0	2.5	3.2
MR 346	K. Kagga/IR8	120	3.1	3.1	3.1
MR 353	K. Kagga/IR8	120	6.1	3.3	4.7
MR 359	K. Kagga/IR8	120	6.4	3.3	4.9
MR 362	K. Kagga/IR8	130	5.4	2.8	4.1
MR 377	K. Kagga/IR8	130	5.6	1.1	3.3
C7		145	4.9	1.2	3.0
SR 26B mutant	SR 26B	140	6.1	2.8	4.4
Madhu	TN1/TKM 6	125	4.2	1.2	2.7
MR 348	K. Kagga/IR8	130	4.7		
MR 358	K. Kagga/IR8	130	5.0		
MR 363	K. Kagga/IR8	120	6.8		
MR 375	K. Kagga/IR8	130	3.8		
MR 376	K. Kagga/IR8	135	5.4		
IR20	Peta ³ /TN1/TKM 6	135	3.5		
Mangala	Jaya/S 317	115	5.4		
MR 261	IRS/Waner 1	130		3.1	
MR 292 F	Jaya/S 317	133		3.1	
MR 340	K. Kagga/IR8	133		3.1	
MR 341	K. Kagga/IR8	132		3.1	
MR 342	K. Kagga/IR8	128		3.1	
IR3541-6-					
PN-58-5-3-1	IR442-2-58/IR1514A-E666// BRJ13-B-55/IR480-5-9-3	130		2.6	
IR40	IR20*2/ O. nivara//CR94-13	130		2.6	
Dasal		126		3.8	
Getu		128		2.7	
SR 26B		142		3.5	

^aDS = dry season; WS = wet season.

Phosphorus-efficient varieties

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The possibility that Texas rice varieties are efficient utilizers of phosphorus (P) would explain the lack of yield increase when P fertilizer is applied to rice grown on seemingly P-deficient soil. Beaumont